

Perceived effectiveness of social networks for job search

Maayan Zhitomirsky-Geffet and Yair Bratspiess

Department of Information Science, Bar-Ilan University

Ramat-Gan, Israel.

Maayan.Zhitomirsky-Geffet@biu.ac.il yairbar@gmail.com

Abstract

One of the most common uses of the social networks' capabilities is for professional, study and business purposes. The literature presents conflicting evidence as to the effectiveness of different networks for professional purposes. Therefore, our primary research aim is to conduct a comparative investigation of the effectiveness and factors which influence the effectiveness of different social networks for finding a job. This study focuses on the two most popular networks, Facebook and LinkedIn; the former is not intended specifically for professional purposes while the latter is. To this end, we conducted a user study based on over 220 responses to a questionnaire especially designed for this goal. In our analysis, we distinguish and compare between the users' perception and attitudes toward the effectiveness of the network and its actual helpfulness for finding a job in the past experience. Our results indicate that different demographic and network usage variables influenced the attitude to effectiveness and helpfulness of the networks. Thus, users with lower incomes preferred Facebook, while more educated users with higher incomes perceived LinkedIn as more effective. Interestingly, we found that despite the fact that LinkedIn was perceived as significantly more effective for finding a job by the majority of the users, the actual helpfulness of the two networks was assessed as quite similar. Our findings provide a direct evidence for bridging social capital

increase by online social networks. This study has practical implications and recommendations that will enable job candidates to improve their job-hunting strategies.

Introduction

The rapidly accelerating development of technology has caused a dramatic development in social media (Gergen, 2005). (Nadkarni and Hofmann, 2012) found that one of the main reasons for the use of social networks is for the purpose of self-promotion and public relations. A comprehensive study by (Di Capua, 2010), that reviewed 100 research studies of Facebook found that at its inception Facebook was used primarily for maintaining contact with friends or family living far away, whereas nowadays Facebook is used for a variety of purposes, including job-hunting, publicity, and the forming of groups with shared areas of interest. As a result, in recent years, social networks have evolved into a commonly used tool in the world of business and careers. Companies search for employees via social networks, and studies have shown that the assessment of a person's professional abilities based on the information he discloses on social networks is usually accurate (Brown and Vaughn, 2011). Universities, government organizations and private companies open network pages in order to promote themselves and to make contact with graduates/employees and employees, and students disclose information about their education and work on the various networks. However, (Roth et al., 2013), point to a dearth in research into the use and effectiveness of social networks for professional and studies-related purposes.

The aim of the present study, therefore, is to investigate which network is perceived as more effective for career promotion by different groups of users and what the underlying reasons are. We will also examine whether the perceived effectiveness of the network is related to the actual helpfulness and use of the network for job-hunting.

Two popular networks, different in nature (Van Dijck, 2013), were chosen for the purposes of the study. The first is Facebook, which is considered to be the most popular in Israel and is of a general social nature. Facebook is the second most visited website, with 2,878,000 visits weekly. It is the leading content site in Israel, since the site most visited is the search engine Google, which has no internal content (according to the TNS TIM survey of website ranking in 2011: <http://www.globes.co.il/en/article-1000652763>). The second is LinkedIn, which is designed specifically for career promotion and job-hunting.

Hence, the research hypotheses of this study are as follows:

1. Differences will be found between the networks in levels of popularity, levels of use, and in the perception of effectiveness for job-hunting.
2. A positive relationship will be found between perception of the network's effectiveness for job-hunting and its actual use and helpfulness for this purpose.
3. A positive relationship will be found between perception of effectiveness and the degree of professional information disclosure on the network.
4. The demographic profile of a user who believes that Facebook is more effective for job-hunting will be different from the demographic profile of a user who believes LinkedIn to be more effective.
5. The demographic profile of a LinkedIn account holder will be different from an individual who does not have an account on this network.

In order to test these hypotheses, a survey was conducted on over 220 participants with different demographic profiles. The survey participants responded to questions about popularity and effectiveness of the two selected networks for work-related and professional purposes. Analysis of the results indicates that most of the research hypotheses are supported by the sample of participants in the survey. Finally, we

performed a logistic regression analysis for each network separately in order to predict which network is perceived as more effective for finding a job according to different variables. The prediction model was found significant for both networks with higher percentage of explained variance for LinkedIn.

In conclusion, this study has practical implications and recommendations that will enable candidates to improve their job searching strategies. For example, different networks will be more helpful in filling vacancies in hi-tech and medicine as opposed to student jobs, or entry-level jobs as opposed to positions for holders of a post-graduate degree. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to assess and compare the attitudes to the effectiveness and actual usage of different social networks for job hunting and career promotion purposes.

The paper continues as follows: The next section reviews previous research in this field; Section 3 presents the research methodology; Section 4 describes the experimental results; and Section 5 analyzes and summarizes the principal findings.

Related Work

The uniqueness of a social network lies in the fact that tools and possibilities that in the past were scattered among different websites are now blended into a single application, on a single website (Boyd and Ellison, 2007). Social networks provide web-based services that enable their users to design a public or private profile within a closed system, to view and select other registered users with whom they can interact in different ways, and to view their contact lists. According to a survey conducted in the USA by the Pew Internet & American Life Project (Hampton et al., 2011), 47% of adult Internet users (aged 30 and above) browse on social networks.

A recent study of social networks found six principal reasons for using social media (Chen and Kim, 2013):

1. Virtual community. Social network users wish to become involved in online discussions and thereby gain a sense of community.
2. Entertainment. People use social networks as a tool for entertainment and enjoyment.
3. Self-presentation. People use social networks in order to present themselves as they wish to be presented. This reason was found in several other studies conducted in the field.
4. Forming ties.
5. Maintaining existing ties. Using social networks for Reasons 4 and 5 is a way of staying up-to-date on the daily activities of their friends, both real and virtual.
6. Searching for information. Users rely on social networks as a means of obtaining information through other people.

In the present study, we investigated whether job-hunting and career advancement are also significant considerations in opening an account on a social network.

To the best of our knowledge no previous research has focused directly on attitudes toward the effectiveness of social networks for finding a job. Therefore, we will now review related papers that address different aspects of professional activity on social networks.

Profiling the networks

Papacharissi (2009) provides a comparative analysis of Facebook, which is defined as a network open to everyone, and LinkedIn as a network with a professional orientation. The comparison focuses on the networks' technological functionality. Facebook enables users to share information with friends by means of status messages, photo-sharing and even contributing applications to be integrated into the website. In contrast, LinkedIn enables users to form a link with new users who are associated with their occupational

field. Unlike Facebook, where every user can become the friend of another user, LinkedIn requires the two users to be acquainted or to have mutual friends in order to become connected. An additional difference between the two networks is the way in which the users present themselves: On Facebook the users can present their hobbies or favorite series, movies or bands. LinkedIn does not provide for these features; the user presents his professional profile, with factual information such as his places of employment and education. According to the study, Facebook is the equivalent of a glasshouse, with a publicly open structure and looser behavioral norms. LinkedIn is tighter and offers less room for spontaneous interaction between users.

Van Dijck (2013) conducted an interface comparison analysis between Facebook and LinkedIn. The author describes the difference that evolves between our real identity and the identity we shape for ourselves on the various social media, such as Facebook and LinkedIn, because of the inducements that have developed over the years on the different networks. The networks provide different tools for self-presentation, self-marketing and expression of the “persona”, and with the help of these tools, we are cajoled into publicizing details about ourselves and to fashion any identity we like. The results of the comparison showed that Facebook focuses on providing its users with tools for self-presentation, whereas LinkedIn tends to cater for professional self-promotion. Despite the difference, both platforms offer similar principles of connectivity and narrative strategies (presenting events as a “live story”), which can be seen as a result of their recent interface adjustments. The study concludes that the networks in question do not provide a neutral platform for self-presentation, since they themselves are a tool for shaping identity, and that it is important to raise users’ awareness of this fact in order to change their approach to the routine use of these tools.

Use of social networks for professional and occupational purposes

Social capital implies that social networks have some value as they are networks of “friends, colleagues and more general contact through whom you receive opportunities to use your financial and human capital” (Burt, 2000; Lesser, 2000). The authors further show that, in particular, one of the most important benefits of social networks is in the area of job hunting, especially based on the “weak social ties” (outside family and close friends). This type of social capital is referred to as *bridging social capital*, which provides access to novel information, such as job opportunities. In the recent studies by (Ellison et al., 2007; Steinfield et al., 2008; Burke et al., 2011) it has been shown that Facebook and other online social networks, which enable users to maintain larger and diffuse networks of relationships, help increase bridging social capital.

Social networks can be easily used for forming business ties and for career promotion. However, to the best of our knowledge, no direct, systematic comparison has yet been conducted of the effectiveness of the different networks for professional purposes. Nevertheless, a number of studies, which we shall review below, have investigated professional activity in the social media.

The use of social networks among professionals has risen dramatically. Studies have examined and compared the effectiveness of the networks for different occupational fields.

According to (Calvó-Armengol and Jackson, 2004) the importance of social media in the work market has expanded considerably. The results of a survey show that 50% of the vacancies in Massachusetts were filled with the help of social networks. The paper examines a model of how job vacancies are advertised on social networks. The model describes network users as “agents” who pass on information about job vacancies to their friends on the social networks. The model also describes how social networks affect the dropout rate from the work market. The paper suggests that the greater the number of social network contacts (agents) a user has, the shorter the time he will need to find a job. The examples also demonstrate that the employment status of the agents (working or unemployed) is important for the user’s search for a

job. Recent studies have shown that job-hunters who spent time looking on social networks had a considerable advantage in finding a new job. Furthermore, the more active they were and the greater number of contacts they had, the greater the likelihood of finding a job through the social network (Greet et al., 2010).

(Benson et al., 2010) carried out a survey among 272 business students in Britain and around the world on the subject of career development and entrepreneurship on social networks. Each survey participant held an account on 1.4 networks on average. Not one undergraduate student from among the participants had a LinkedIn account. The majority of the participants (214) said that Facebook was the principal network that they used in order to advance their career. The results of the survey reveal critical differences between undergraduates, graduates and student communities around the world. The survey shows that undergraduates tended to use social networks for social purposes to a greater degree than graduates, whereas graduates tended to use social networks for business purposes to a greater degree than undergraduates. The difference between the groups can be attributed to the average age of each group: 22 years old for undergraduates and 29 for graduates. With regard to national differences, the survey showed that British students see social networks as a tool for job-hunting or promoting business interests to a lesser degree than students from outside Britain, who, on the whole, named LinkedIn as an effective tool for finding work. In contrast, (Madge et al., 2009) report that students who took part in their survey used Facebook primarily for social, not study-related, purposes.

Senior faculty members have also discovered social networks. A survey conducted among 1921 senior faculty members found that at least 90% of them were aware of the existence of the leading social media such as LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook, and that some 50% of participants had visited Facebook at least once in the preceding month, 40% of whom had posted content. 45% of them reported using Facebook for professional purposes and 11% reported daily use of the media for professional purposes. Approximately

58% agree that social media play an important role in expanding learning (Moran et al., 2011). With regard to seniority, the study found that the percentage of less experienced teaching faculty who made use of social networks is higher than that of more experienced faculty members. 78% of participants reported using at least one social network for professional purposes.

(Breeding, 2009) compares the effectiveness of the different networks for the professional needs of librarians. He discovered that, despite the large number of librarians who use Facebook, this social network focuses more on leisure activities and less on sharing professional information. LinkedIn is also a very popular social network site among librarians. The purpose of this social network is to build and develop the careers of its users. It is useful for making contacts within a particular occupational field, mainly by using the service that enables two unconnected users to be “introduced” via a mutual friend. It also allows one user to recommend another, which may also contribute to the process of finding work. Despite the success of Facebook and LinkedIn, the author finds that Twitter is the best social network for receiving updates in his fields of interest. This network also enables the professional librarian to achieve effective exposure within a short time. Companies that deal in library-related products and services post tweets in order to advertise new books and new products and to publicize press releases.

Using social networks for recruiting workers

Almost all the large companies in the United States use the Internet for recruiting workers (Cappelli, 2001). The Internet enables the company recruiter to locate a large number of suitable candidates for every kind of job with relative ease, to screen them quickly and contact candidates directly. (Palank, 2006) found that employers searching for information about potential candidates commonly use social networks, especially Facebook, since the information posted on this network is usually personal rather than professional and employers can therefore form an impression of the candidate’s character.

(Skeels et al., 2009) investigated different attitudes and behaviors within a large technology organization using a survey and focused interviews. The researchers found widespread use of social media for both social and professional purposes. They believe that, despite the difficulty in proving a relationship between social networks and the productivity of company employees, many companies will begin using social media within the organization. However, (Breeding, 2009) reports that since LinkedIn can be helpful to people searching for information about a certain company or organization, certain companies do not allow their employees to open a LinkedIn account, so as to prevent their competitors from “poaching” their workers.

In summary, it can be seen that different studies indicate the advantages of the different networks as a tool for recruiting workers, job-hunting and professional activity in different occupational fields. In order to obtain a clearer picture, in this paper we shall conduct a direct, systematic investigation of the relationship between perception of effectiveness, patterns of use, popularity, and actual helpfulness of both of the networks that were chosen, using a heterogeneous sample comprised of subjects of different professions, ages, income and educational levels.

Research Methodology

An on-line questionnaire was designed for the purpose of the study. The complete questionnaire can be found in the appendix.

There are four main groups of questions in the questionnaire. The first group contains demographic questions (Items 1-10). The second group consists of questions about habits of network usage (Items 11-14, 25, 26, 31-33). The third group relates to the main research goal, namely, the effectiveness of the network as a tool for job-hunting or career advancement (Items 27-30, 34-35). The fourth group examines the degree of personal professional information disclosure on the network (Items 15-24).

We define a multivariable model for comparative evaluation of social network effectiveness. The model includes several types of independent variables such as demographic details, variables related to network usage habits (e.g. hours on the net) and patterns of information disclosure (corresponding to item groups 1, 2 and 4 above). The dependent variables of the model relate to the networks' effectiveness for job-hunting (corresponding to item group 3 above). In particular, the dependent variables were divided into two subgroups: 1) user perception of effectiveness; and 2) actual helpfulness of the network for finding a job. We further examine the relationship and mutual impact of these two subgroups.

Questionnaire validation method

To validate our questionnaire the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of internal consistency was calculated for the following two subgroups of questions from group 4, since each of these groups reflects a similar aspect of the survey:

Occupation-related details disclosed are represented by items 19-22, 23-24. Responses were coded with the values 0=no/no account, 1=yes. The variable was composed of the number of the disclosed items — the larger the total, the greater the amount of work details disclosed. A test of internal consistency reliability (Cronbach's α coefficient values) showed that the reliability of the variable in the present sample was $\alpha = 0.82$ for Facebook and $\alpha = 0.74$ for LinkedIn.

Education-related details disclosed are represented by items 23-24, 15-18. Responses were coded with the values 0=no/no account, 1=yes. The variable was composed of the number of the disclosed details — the larger the total, the greater the amount of education details disclosed. A test of internal consistency reliability showed that the reliability of the variable in the present sample was $\alpha = 0.78$ for Facebook and $\alpha = 0.74$ for LinkedIn.

Note that the internal consistency was calculated for the above factors for every social network separately, as we did not expect subjects to exhibit similar behavior on different networks.

We conclude that the internal consistencies assessed using the Cronbach's alpha coefficient ranged from 0.74 to 0.82 and are thus considered acceptable (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994).

Sample population

For the purpose of the study, a research population of 222 subjects who had an account at least on one of the two social networks was recruited, comprised of individuals of different ages, demographic background and a variety of professions. We deliberately distributed the questionnaire through several technological means, in order to prevent skewing of the results and to reach individuals who do not have an account on some of the social networks.

Distribution was carried out as follows: 1) personal e-mails to all addresses in the authors' address books; 2) a post on the authors' Facebook, Google+ and LinkedIn accounts; 3) posts on professional forums to ensure a certain number of participants from a particular professional field, e.g. a nurses, psychologists and lawyers forums on the popular portal Tapuz; 4) direct application to friends from specific fields/companies, such as technology companies Ness and SAP, Wolfson Hospital, Harel Insurance company, Leumi Bank, and Bar Ilan University (lecturers and students). In addition, all the above e-mails included a request to forward the e-mail to friends of the addressees, thereby yielding a secondary distribution. This study received ethics approval and was conducted in accordance with the American Psychology Association (APA) ethical requirements. Participants could complete the online survey anonymously from any personal computer. Table 1 below presents the socioeconomic characteristics of the sample.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the sample (N=222).

<i>Variable</i>		<i>Percentage</i>	<i>N</i>
		%	
Gender	Male	45.5%	101
	Female	54.5%	121
Age	30-18	32.8%	73
	31-40	48.2%	107
	41-50	9.5%	21
	51+	9.5%	21
Marital status	Single	47.3%	105
	Married	45.9%	102
	Divorced	6.8%	15
Education	No degree (up to 12 years education, practical engineer, undergraduate student)	32.0%	71
	Bachelor's degree	40.0%	89
	Master's degree and above	28.0%	62
Employed	No	9.0%	20
	Yes	91.0%	202
Occupational field	Hi-tech	29.3%	65
	Academic/teaching	11.3%	25
	Liberal professions (medicine, law, engineering)	9.5%	21

	Economics/ insurance/accounting/ management/marketing/sales	%11.7	26
	Administration/business services	7.7%	17
	Industry/skilled craftsman/unskilled labor	5.4%	12
	Nursing/social work	%7.7	17
	Other	%17.6	39
Monthly income	Up to 6,000 shekels	%31.1	69
	6,001-10,500	%29.7	66
	10,501-15,000	%18.0	40
	15,001+	%21.2	47
Work seniority	Up to one year	%23.9	53
	1-3	%30.2	67
	4-7	%24.8	55
	8+	%21.1	47

Analysis and Results

In this section we will describe the findings of the statistical analysis we performed in order to test the research hypotheses presented above. Our findings show that 23% of Facebook users and 30% of LinkedIn users in our sample indicated that one of the reasons for opening an account on a social network was to find a salaried job. Interestingly, the predominant reasons for opening an account on both networks were the traditional ones of keeping in touch with old friends and sharing information with friends (more than 60% mentioned these reasons with regard to both networks).

Patterns of usage and popularity

Firstly, in order to examine Hypothesis 1, we shall analyze the levels of popularity and usage (hours spent online) in general for each network.

The data presented in the table shows that Facebook is the social network to which the overwhelming majority of the sample (216 out of 222 subjects, 97.3%) belongs. Slightly more than half of the subjects (126 subjects, 56.8%) belong to LinkedIn. 53.6% (119 out of 222) of the subjects have accounts on both networks.

The table below presents data concerning the number of hours spent online and on social networks.

Table 2: Hours spent online and on social networks

Hours spent online	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>sd</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>
	<i>No. of subjects</i>	<i>Average</i>			
On the Internet (average per day)	222	3.67	3.17	0.00	19.00
On social networks	222	1.64	2.35	0.00	17.00
On Facebook	216	1.40	2.10	0.00	12.00
On LinkedIn	126	0.08	0.34	0.00	3.00

The data shows that subjects in the sample report spending an average of 3-4 hours daily on the Internet, with an average of one and a half hours on Facebook and about ten minutes on LinkedIn. The similar numbers were obtained for the 119 subjects who hold an account on both networks.

Perception of the networks' effectiveness for professional purposes

Figure 1 below presents the distribution of subjects' responses to the general question: "Do you consider social networks to be effective for job-hunting?" (corresponding to Item 34 in the questionnaire).

Figure 1: Perception of social networks as effective for job-hunting.

The data shown on Figure 1 indicates that the majority of subjects (approximately 75%) report that they consider a social network to be at least somewhat effective in the process of job-hunting. Furthermore, 39% of them consider a social network to be significantly effective for job-hunting. We also compared the perceived effectiveness of the social network for job-hunting of the employed and unemployed subjects. Twenty two of the subjects were unemployed. We found that significantly less percentage of unemployed subjects perceived social networks as somewhat effective (59% vs. 75%) and substantially effective (32% vs. 39%) than of the employed subjects.

Most of the subjects in the full sample, 58%, report that in their opinion, LinkedIn is the most effective social network for job-hunting (Item 35) while 42% chose Facebook as the most effective. Facebook has been perceived as more effective by unemployed subjects than by employed subjects (52% vs. 42%), while LinkedIn has been perceived as more effective by employed subjects than by unemployed subjects (58% vs. 48%).

In order to neutralize the effect of membership of only one of the networks, we also investigated which network is considered to be more effective by the majority of subjects with an account on both networks. It transpired that subjects with an account on both Facebook and LinkedIn (83.7%) perceive LinkedIn to be more effective, although most of the subjects who have an account solely on Facebook (66.2% of them) consider Facebook to be more effective. It is interesting to note that approximately one third of subjects with an account solely on Facebook (and no account on LinkedIn) still perceive LinkedIn as being more effective.

Analysis according to demographic data yielded significant differences according to age ($\chi^2(3) = 15.60$, $p < 0.01$), income ($\chi^2(2) = 39.71$, $p < 0.01$) and education ($\chi^2(2) = 15.94$, $p < 0.01$). Thus, most of the young subjects (up to age 30) with lower income levels (of up to 10,500 shekels) and no academic degree (with a high-school or vocational education, and students) perceive Facebook as more effective for job-hunting and career advancement, whereas most of the older subjects (over the age of 30) with higher incomes and higher education (bachelor's or post-graduate degree) consider LinkedIn to be more effective than Facebook for these purposes.

We conclude that these findings support Hypotheses 1 and 4, namely, that there are differences between different demographic groups in their perception of effectiveness for job-hunting.

Level of usage and actual helpfulness as factors in attitudes to effectiveness

In addition to the perception of effectiveness, we examined the extent to which the networks were actually helpful for job-hunting. Most of the subjects (131 subjects, 59%) reported not having found work through a social network and 91 subjects (41%) reported having found a job with the help of a social network (Item 28). Employed subjects tried using social networks for job-hunting more than unemployed subjects (40% vs.

31% for item 27). However, there was no significant difference between employed and unemployed subjects for having found a job in the past with the help of a social network (item 28).

Subjects were also asked about the helpfulness of each network separately for finding work (Item 29: Did one of the social networks ever actually help you find work either directly or indirectly?). The subjects were asked to recall whether one of the social networks had actually helped them find a job in the past. This question represents the network’s actual effectiveness based on facts as opposed to the perceived effectiveness, which reflects the attitudes or feelings of the subjects toward the different networks. The responses are detailed according to social network in Table 3.

Table 3: Distribution of the social network’s helpfulness in finding work (N=222).

Did the social network help you find work in the past?	Facebook		LinkedIn	
	Percentage %	N	Percentage %	N
No	62.6	139	73.0	162
Yes	37.4	83	27.0	60

The data shown in the table indicates that Facebook leads in helpfulness for finding work; 37.4% of the subjects report that Facebook helped them find a job in the past, while only 27% report that LinkedIn had helped them. In order to neutralize the effect of subjects with an account only on one of the networks (which favors Facebook) we performed a similar analysis on a sample of subjects with an account on both networks. However, although these subjects with accounts on both networks report that LinkedIn was more

helpful in the past for job-hunting (47.9%) than Facebook (37%), these differences were not found to be significant ($\chi^2(1) = 3.72, p > 0.05$). In other words, even participants with a LinkedIn account found Facebook to be helpful to the same extent approximately as LinkedIn and do not report having benefited solely from LinkedIn in their search for work.

Another question included in the survey examined use of the network by evaluating changes in the level of activity on the network (increases, remains constant or decreases, Items 36, 37) during actual job-hunting. We found that the majority (56%) of subjects with an account on both networks report that their level of activity on Facebook remains constant when they are job-hunting and only 30% increase their usage level, whereas on LinkedIn, the usage level of 73% of these subjects rose during job-hunting. These differences were found to be significant ($\chi^2(4) = 38.82, p < 0.01$). However, the following reservation should be made regarding this finding: Under normal circumstances, the amount of time spent browsing on LinkedIn is much lower than on Facebook (see Table 2) and it increases while job-hunting, whereas surfers usually spend a great deal of time on Facebook and therefore the change that occurs when job-hunting is negligible.

In addition, a chi-square test revealed significant differences with regard to which of the social networks is perceived as more effective for job-hunting according to usage level while job-hunting on LinkedIn alone ($\chi^2(2) = 7.98, p < 0.05$). The overwhelming majority of subjects who reported that their usage level on the network while job-hunting increases (%84.3) or remains constant (%62.5) chose LinkedIn as the more effective network, whereas only 41.7% of subjects who reported a decrease in LinkedIn activity chose LinkedIn. With regard to the level of Facebook activity while job-hunting, no significant differences were found as to which of the social networks is perceived as the more effective for job-hunting.

A chi-square test also revealed significant differences with regard to which of the social networks is perceived as more effective for job-hunting according to the network's helpfulness in the past in finding a job. Among subjects who reported that Facebook did not help them find work in the past, only 37.2%

perceived Facebook as the more effective network, while most of the subjects who reported that Facebook had helped them to find a job in the past chose Facebook as the more effective network (%52.4) ($\chi^2 (1)= 4.74, p<0.05$).

Similarly, most of the subjects who considered Facebook to be more effective reported that LinkedIn had not helped them find work in the past (82.1%), whereas most of the subjects who perceived LinkedIn as more effective reported that LinkedIn had helped them find a job in the past (55.1%). Nevertheless, approximately half of the subjects who reported that it had not helped them in the past (44.9%) chose LinkedIn as the more effective network ($\chi^2 (1)= 4.74, p<0.05$).

Thus, Hypothesis 2 (that a positive influence exists between perception of effectiveness and actual use for job-hunting) is supported by our findings for both networks.

The relationship between perceived and actual effectiveness and professional information disclosure

Analysis of the findings demonstrates that the majority of the subjects (over 60%) post personal professional information on both social networks. However, the likelihood of LinkedIn account holders posting personal education-related (89.7%) and work-related (88.1%) information is greater than for Facebook account holders (69% and 60.2% respectively).

In this section, we examine Hypothesis 3, which posits that a correlation exists between a social network's effectiveness in finding a job/career advancement and professional information disclosure on that network. The findings of a t-test for independent samples demonstrate that in all cases when subjects had found a network to be helpful in finding work in the past, they disclosed significantly more details on it, as compared

to subjects who reported that the network had not been helpful. The t-test values for Facebook are: -3.53** for education-related details, -4.80** for occupation-related details, and for LinkedIn: -2.36* for education-related details and -4.60** for occupation-related details, at significance levels of $p < 0.01^{**}$, $p < 0.05^*$, respectively.

In view of the above findings, we conclude that a positive influence exist between the degree of professional information disclosure and both Facebook's and LinkedIn's actual helpfulness and perceived effectiveness.

Predicting perception of a network’s effectiveness according to the different variables

Finally, we performed a logistic regression analysis for each network separately in order to predict which network is perceived as effective for finding a job according to variables of socio-demographic background, social factors (contacts with work colleagues and with the page of the company where the subject is employed), and user habits (hours spent online, activity level while job-hunting, actual helpfulness in finding work). Table 4 below shows the findings of the regression analyses.

Table 4: Coefficients of logistic regression for predicting the social network’s effectiveness in job-hunting among LinkedIn users.

Dependent variable: which network is effective?				
Coefficients				
Predictors	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Wald</i>	<i>Exp(B)</i>
			<i>(df=1)</i>	<i>(Odds Ratio)</i>

Age	0.29	0.17	2.68	1.33
Income	0.10	0.09	1.10	1.10
Education	-0.14	0.21	0.49	0.86
Education-related information	0.35	0.32	1.17	1.42
Occupation-related information	0.03	0.21	0.02	1.03
Public access – education	0.66	0.60	1.20	1.94
Public access – occupation	-0.32	0.61	0.27	0.72
Link to company page	-0.17	0.73	0.05	0.84
Work colleagues	1.09	0.55	3.59*	2.98
Hours spent online	0.01	0.07	0.01	1.00
Hours on LinkedIn	19.56	0.26	0.01	0.74
Helpfulness in finding work	1.83	0.67	7.43**	6.29

As the data in the table shows, the findings of the logistic regression for predicting the perception of LinkedIn as the more effective network indicate that individuals who are connected to their work colleagues on the network are 2.98 times more likely to perceive LinkedIn as more effective than people who are not connected to work colleagues. Similarly, subjects who found LinkedIn to be helpful in the past for finding work are 6.29 times more likely to perceive LinkedIn as more effective as compared with those for whom the network was not helpful for job-hunting. The prediction model was found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2(12) = 37.82, p < 0.00$) and the percentage of explained variance to be 28%.

The findings of the logistic regression for predicting the perception of Facebook as the more effective network indicate that for every increase in unit of income, the perception of Facebook as more effective becomes 0.78 times less likely (or alternatively, the perception of Facebook as more effective becomes 0.78 times more likely). The prediction model was found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2(6) = 42.44, p < 0.00$) and the percentage of explained variance to be 15%. This result indicates that some other factors play a role in the perception of Facebook's effectiveness like its high popularity.

Demographic profiling of LinkedIn users vs. users without an account on LinkedIn

Finally, for the purpose of testing Hypothesis 5, we investigated differences between the sub-sample of LinkedIn account-holders and the sub-sample of those without a LinkedIn account. 126 subjects have a LinkedIn account and 96 other subjects from the sample have no LinkedIn account. Significant differences were found between LinkedIn users and those with no LinkedIn account regarding gender ($\chi^2(1) = 10.09, p < 0.01$). Among members of LinkedIn 54.8% were men and 45.2% women, while those with no LinkedIn account were comprised of 66.7% women and 33.3% men.

Significant differences were found between LinkedIn account holders and those without a LinkedIn account with regard to education ($\chi^2(6) = 15.04, p < 0.05$). While most LinkedIn members have a bachelor's degree (31%), 27.8% have a master's degree, 16.7% are undergraduate students and 10.3% are master's students, only 16.7% among those without a LinkedIn account have a master's degree, 11.5% have a practical engineering degree and 11.5% have a high school education or less.

Significant differences were also found between LinkedIn account holders and those without a LinkedIn account with regard to income ($\chi^2(10) = 34.56, p < 0.01$). While 17.5% of LinkedIn members have an income of between 12,000-15,000 shekels, 13.5% an income of over 25,000 shekels, 11.95% between 2,001-7,500 shekels, 9.5% between 15,001-20,000 shekels and only 12.7% earn less than 3,000 shekels, among those

without a LinkedIn account income levels are lower – 26% have an income of less than 3,000 shekels, 16.7% earn between 4,501-6,000 shekels, 13.5% between 7,501-9,000 shekels and 11.5% between 6,001-7,500 shekels. A t-test also found significant differences in salary levels ($t(220) = -5.46$, $p < 0.01$). Among LinkedIn account holders, the average salary level was 5.49 (SD=3.22) (ranging from 9,000-12,000 shekels), whereas among users without a LinkedIn account, the average salary level was 3.22 (SD=2.85) (ranging from 6,000-7,500 shekels).

Significant differences were found between LinkedIn account holders and those without a LinkedIn account with regard to current employment status ($\chi^2(1) = 4.23$, $p < 0.01$). 94.4% of LinkedIn account holders are working, while only 86.5% of those without a LinkedIn account are working.

Finally, significant differences were found between LinkedIn account holders and those without a LinkedIn account with regard to occupational field ($\chi^2(8) = 61.95$, $p < 0.01$). Among LinkedIn account holders, 46.8% work in hi-tech, 11.9% in management/marketing/sales, and 9.5% in academic/teaching professions. Among those without a LinkedIn account, 22.9% work in a job that falls into the category of “other occupations”, 14.6% in nursing/caring professions, 13.5% in administration and service occupations, 13.5% in academic/teaching professions, 12.5% in the liberal professions, and only 6.3% in hi-tech.

However, no significant differences were found with regard to age and marital status.

Discussion and Conclusions

We conducted a comprehensive, in-depth study of the effectiveness of two social networks for professional purposes in Israel. The networks chosen, Facebook and LinkedIn, differ in character and purpose. Both of

them are actually used by their members to find jobs and promote their career. However, previous literature reports controversial evidence as to the different networks' effectiveness for the above purposes. The advantage of Facebook is its high popularity while the strength of LinkedIn is its explicit professional orientation. The main research question was therefore which of the networks is perceived as more effective by the users and which one is actually more effective in practice. We defined a multivariable model for social network effectiveness evaluation and comparison. Based on this model, five research hypotheses were tested by means of a users' questionnaire that was analyzed using commonly accepted statistical tools. The results of this analysis demonstrated that our hypotheses were supported by the research findings. Further, the logistic regression model based on the defined variables for prediction of the social network effectiveness for finding a job was significant with connections to work colleagues and actual helpfulness as the most contributing factors for LinkedIn.

In particular, analysis of the results shows that LinkedIn, with its specifically professional orientation, does in fact outrank Facebook, which does not have a specifically professional orientation, with regard to attitude toward effectiveness, increase of usage while job-hunting, and the amount of personal professional information disclosed. In addition, LinkedIn users are characterized by higher educational and income levels and a more limited range of professions, such as hi-tech (than those who do not have an account on LinkedIn), and therefore appears to be an "elitist" network. However, on Facebook too, more than 60% of the survey participants disclosed professional information, more than 40% of the participants perceived it as more effective for job-hunting than LinkedIn (mainly young people with lower levels of income and academic education), and approximately 45% counted work colleagues among their friends on Facebook. Facebook is much more popular in terms of number of users and number of browsing hours and almost twice as many people (more than 95% of the sample) had an account on this network, as compared with only about a half who had a LinkedIn account. Hence, despite the fact that LinkedIn is perceived as being more effective,

surprisingly, its levels of actual helpfulness in finding work were similar to those of Facebook and no significant difference was found between the networks.

We found that users who post more professional information about themselves also report higher levels of actual helpfulness for both networks. In addition, employed subjects perceive social networks as more effective for job hunting and use them more for this purposes than the unemployed subjects. Employed subjects also disclose more professional information about themselves on Facebook and more of them open up LinkedIn accounts. These findings support the previous research on social capital of online social networks and provide a direct evidence for the statement that they increase bridging social capital in the area of job opportunities.

Therefore, as practical recommendation, the results of our survey suggest that in Israel, users who believe in social networks effectiveness and use them for job hunting are more likely to find a job and be employed. Facebook is actually not less effective than LinkedIn. For users interested in jobs with higher incomes, more senior positions and technological professional are recommended to use LinkedIn in addition to Facebook. We also conclude that posting more information on both social networks is advantageous in order to raise the network's effectiveness for finding work.

In the future, we intend to extend this study to other countries and social networks, and also to explore their effectiveness for companies and worker recruiters.

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Appendix

Full questionnaire:

1. Do you have a Facebook account?

• Yes • No

2. Do you have a LinkedIn account?

• Yes • No

3. How old are you?

18-99

4. What gender are you?

• Male • Female

5. What is your marital status?

Single Married Divorced Widow/er

6. What education do you have?

Up to 12 years' schooling Practical engineer Bachelors' student Bachelors' degree Masters' student

Masters' degree Doctorate student PhD

7. What is your income?

0-3000 3001-4500 4501-6000 6001-7500 7501-9000 9001-10500 10501-12000

12001-15000 15001-20000 20001-25000 25001+

8. Are you currently employed?

• Yes • No

9. What field do you work in?

asa) Heavy industry b) Hi-tech c) Law d) Medicine e) Accountancy f) Economics g) Teaching h) Skilled craftsman/woman j) Insurance k) Unskilled labor l) Customer service
m) Clerical work n) Marketing Management Sales o) Engineering p) Biotechnology
q) Physics r) Chemistry s) Nursing and paramedical professions t) Pharmacy u) Social work v)
Communications x) Political science w) Psychology y) Information science z) Other

10. How many years have you worked at your current place of work?

0-1 1-3 3-5 5-7 7-9 9-11 11-15 15+

11. How many hours a day on average do you spend on the Internet?

0-24

12. How many hours of your daily Internet browsing do you spend on social networks?

0-24

13. How many hours of your daily Internet browsing do you spend on Facebook?

0-24

14. How many hours of your daily Internet browsing do you spend on LinkedIn?

0-24

15. Are details about your education disclosed on Facebook?

• Yes • No

16. If details about your education are disclosed on Facebook, what authorization is needed to see them?

a) Public b) Friends only c) Private

17. Are details about your education disclosed on LinkedIn?

• Yes • No

18. If details about your education are disclosed on LinkedIn, what authorization is needed to see them?

a) Public b) Friends only c) Private

19. Are details about your occupation disclosed on Facebook?

• Yes • No

20. If details about your occupation are disclosed on Facebook, what authorization is needed to see them?

a) Public b) Friends only c) Private

21. Are details about your occupation disclosed on LinkedIn?

• Yes • No

22. If details about your occupation are disclosed on LinkedIn, what authorization is needed to see them?

a) Public b) Friends only c) Private

23. If you have a Facebook account what personal details did you publish on Facebook?

• First name • Family name • Marital status • Profile picture • Date of birth • Current place of residence •

Previous place of residence • Occupational field • Current job

• Previous job • Position • Academic degree • Present place of study • Previous places of study • Other

24. If you have a LinkedIn account what personal details did you publish on LinkedIn?

• First name • Family name • Marital status • Profile picture • Date of birth • Current place of residence •

Previous place of residence • Occupational field • Current job

• Previous job • Position • Academic degree • Present place of study • Previous places of study • Other

25. If you have a Facebook account, where do you know most of your friends on Facebook from?

• Kindergarten • Neighborhood • School • Army • Higher education • Previous job • Current job • Other

26. If you have a LinkedIn account, where do you know most of your friends on LinkedIn from?

• Kindergarten • Neighborhood • School • Army • Higher education • Previous job • Current job • Other

27. Have you used a social network to help you find work?*

• Yes

• No

28. Did social networks help you find work in the past?

- Yes • No

29. Did one of the social networks ever actually help you find work either directly or indirectly?*

- Facebook
- LinkedIn
- A social network has never helped me find work

30. What were your main reasons to open a social network account?*

- To make new friends
- To find old friends
- To store photos
- To store videos
- To share personal information
- To be able to spread information to a large number of friends quickly and with a single action
- To find work (as a salaried worker)
- To advertise my business
- To find a boy/girl friend
- To keep up to date on topics related to my studies
- Other

31. Does the company where you work have a page on a social network?*

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

32. If your company has a page on Facebook, is your personal account linked to the company page?*

- Yes
- No
- I don't have an account on this network

33. If your company has a page on LinkedIn, is your personal account linked to the company page?*

- Yes
- No
- I don't have an account on this network

34. Do you consider a social network to be effective for job-hunting?*

- No • Not very effective • Quite effective • Effective • Very effective • No opinion

35. Which social network do you consider to be the most effective for job-hunting?*

- Facebook
- LinkedIn

36. When you are job-hunting do you spend more time on Facebook?*

- Less -Same -More -I don't have an account with this social network

37. When you are job-hunting do you use LinkedIn more?

- Less -Same -More -I don't have an account with this social network